

“YANGI ASR” - ILMIY-METODIK JURNALI

1 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

“НОВЫЙ ВЕК” - НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 1, НОМЕР 1

“NEW CENTURY” - SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1

“YANGI ASR” – ILMİY-METODİK JURNALI

“НОВЫЙ ВЕК” – НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | “NEW CENTURY” – SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL

№1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2023-1>

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YANGI ASR

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NEW CENTURY - SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL

ILMIY-METODIK JURNALI

ISSN: 0000-0000

www.tadqiqot.uz

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SOFT SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL WITH A FOCUS ON NEW TECHNOLOGIES THROUGH CRITICAL PEDAGOGY

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8145886>

ABSTRACT

Soft skills are already important in people's daily socioeconomic lives and are expected to become even more important in the coming years. Unlike so-called "hard skills," they can be applied and exploited in a wide range of areas and issues. As a result, their development through the education system is critical for future citizens. Furthermore, the integration of Soft Skills with new technologies will expand opportunities for their development in the classroom and increase student participation. The development of the above in light of Critical Pedagogy is a proposal that prioritizes students who are not afforded the same opportunities by the educational system, while also approaching everyday problems in a novel way. As a result, the effort to solve them is combined with the development of Soft Skills. In this thesis, educational material was created and evaluated by students in the fifth grade of primary school through semi-structured interviews, yielding positive results in terms of the initial purpose and requests.

Introduction

The role of education is especially important in an increasingly rapidly developing world, where today's needs and requirements are expected to be very different from those of tomorrow. Thus, adaptation and flexibility are frequently mentioned words in texts that attempt to approach developments in various fields. One of the primary goals of education is to provide tomorrow's citizens with the necessary supplies, to comprehensively shape their character, and to acquire skills that will be useful in the labor market arena. According to Thacker and Yost (2002), Soft Skills and the effort to cultivate them through the educational system will be useful not only immediately, but much more in the long run in the students' lives. Al-Mamun (2012) adds that "Soft Skills" are the cornerstone for 21st century citizens. Through the development of Soft Skills in school, students can take on a new role in the learning process, making it more enjoyable and creative for them. Thus, the development of teamwork skills can be combined with play, and through this process, students can understand the possibilities offered by teamwork in achieving a goal that would be extremely difficult to achieve by a single person (Attakorn et al, 2013). The development of this skill appears to be useful today in many areas and branches of work, and its role is expected to be even more pivotal in the coming years, as the orientation that exists is the formation of groups of different specialties to approach complex problems. Another critical aspect of Soft Skills is their relationship with Lifelong Learning. People's lives are currently marked by rapid changes in many aspects of their daily lives. As a result, the knowledge they have in a field no longer appears to be useful to them for the rest of their adult lives. On the contrary, they are frequently forced to learn about and become acquainted

with new objects. Lifelong Learning is a necessary but painful condition for them. On the contrary, it appears that as Soft Skills develop, people become more adaptable and willing to learn new subjects and apply their knowledge in new contexts (Tang, et al., 2015). In Greek reality, the emphasis is on the development of cognitive skills rather than soft skills. However, this has negative consequences, as many researchers report that a more weighted distribution is required, as skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, decision making, and teamwork appear to play a very important role in the lives of students and future citizens in relation to cognitive background (Claxton et al., 2016). These abilities can be beneficial in a variety of applications and everyday situations. As a result, for several years they have been placed in the spotlight and included in the programs of the world's most important educational systems. One issue that emerges from many surveys is the background of teachers in order to support an effort regarding integration and the systematic effort to develop Soft Skills in today's school (Tang et al., 2014). Traditional teaching methods, as well as the educational materials with which teachers have been working for decades, place a heavy emphasis on the development of students' cognitive skills while falling far short of the development of soft skills. As a result, it is necessary to train teachers and provide them with material and technical equipment so that they can reshape their teaching models and incorporate the development of soft skills into them (Onabamiro et al., 2014). Soft skills gradually emerge, and goals for their development are established. Although there were no references to them for many years, the introduction of the Skills Workshops has made direct references to them, and it is now necessary to develop them in relation to the learning objectives. They are also integrated into the Greek educational system because they are directly related to students' daily lives and needs both now and in the future. It also appears that learning objects can be taught with the same ease by incorporating soft skills, while learning becomes more enjoyable for students and, as a result, they play a more active role. This is one of the main goals of any educational method (Weber et al., 2009).

Soft Skills

Delineating the term soft skills is difficult because there are many different definitions because researchers approach them from different perspectives. An effort that we believe contains the main elements for this paper is: Soft skills are skills, abilities, and characteristics that an individual possesses and can use throughout his life, regardless of his work environment (Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, 2010). Another definition presented by Unesco supplements the previous one by including a set of intangible personal characteristics, attitudes, and behaviors that can be applied in a variety of professional settings (Unesco, 2013). One of the main characteristics of soft skills is that their development benefits the person throughout his life and a variety of daily issues. According to the researcher's findings, there are skills that are transferred and follow the person. This is one of their strengths. They are not only based on educational system requirements, but also on students' adult lives. As a result, and in the context of this work, where Critical Pedagogy is also involved, we believe that their development is critical. Soft skill development differs from hard skill development. Hard skills are those that can be taught and have a level of knowledge certification. They are the ones that can be used in adulthood.

Soft skills are those related to social skills, communication, and behavioral management. People's development allows them to improve in many areas, including work, social, and even companionship. Hard skills, as opposed to soft skills, are more directly related to technical or administrative issues and are more easily measurable. This is one of the reasons why, with the exception of the mild ones, education systems are given more weight in their development. They are also easier to develop through a structured curriculum than mild ones, which take longer to develop, and their development is associated with various activities that do not involve memorization. In general, soft or life skills are difficult to observe, quantify, and measure.

Hard skills are distinct from soft skills in that they can be easily counted. Their development, in conjunction with the mild ones, provides the individual with significantly more options. As a result, they form a different direction than mild ones.

Soft skill types

Soft skills are a skill web with no set number. As a result, different classifications exist depending on each scholar's perspective and field of study. This thesis will present the soft skills that are directly related to primary education and are considered particularly important for both the minor and adult lives of students in the context of Critical Pedagogy. In the field of education, Lippman et al. (2015) define 'soft skills' as the following skills, each with a brief analysis of its content:

Social skills

Social skills are the abilities we use every day to interact and communicate with others. They include both verbal and nonverbal communication, such as speech, gesture, facial expression, and body language. The ability to know the right and appropriate ways to behave depending on the situation and situations is linked to the development of social skills. Furthermore, understanding communication rules is one of the most important social skills because it relates to the image that a person projects outwardly (Dowd & Tierney, 2005).

A person's social skills enable him to broaden his circle of contacts and easily form new relationships. This skill is becoming increasingly important in primary school students, but also in older students. Thus, the formation of relationships and, through them, friendships with other people aids in the balanced development of the individual. When difficulties arise, a child must be able to implement appropriate strategies, such as conflict resolution. It is also important for children to have empathy, or to be able to put themselves in the shoes of others and recognize their feelings (Oladokun & Gbadegesin, 2017).

With the modern challenges that the school environment faces, such as diversity, student aggression, and so on, empathy becomes increasingly important, and efforts should be made to develop it through all lessons (Reynolds et al., 2010).

Critical thinking

The NCECT defines critical thinking as "the mentally disciplined process of actively and skillfully capturing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information collected from, or produced by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication, as a guide to belief and action" (NCECT, 2014). Students can analyze and evaluate information they receive from their environment and form their own opinions by developing critical thinking skills. Furthermore, critical thinking assists students in formulating questions and searching for answers by synthesizing the information available to them. In today's world of abundant but incorrect information, developing critical thinking skills has become a major issue (Humphries & Kosse, 2017).

Critical thinking skills are developed in primary school, allowing students to develop problem-solving strategies and apply knowledge from other fields to achieve their goals. Critical thinking is one of the high-level skills. The practical value of critical thinking skills is the application of these skills to solve problems that allow rational decision-making to enhance successful human activities (Reynolds, 2012).

Problem solving

As previously stated, problem solving is closely linked to the development of critical thinking. More specifically, "problem solving" refers to the process and strategies that students devise and implement in order to find a solution to "structured" problems or unclear problematic situations (Cassidy & Long, 1996). The goal is to tailor their strategy to the needs of problematic situations. As a result, developing problem-solving skills is a difficult process that adheres to traditional teaching standards via molds. It is a skill whose ultimate goal is to enable students to deal autonomously with similar situations using the acquired knowledge (Matsangouras, 2007).

Although the development of this skill, as mentioned above, is very complex, it does have certain stages that are followed in most problems and can be captured as follows: Initially, the essence of the problem or problematic situation is identified. Then, as much information about the topic as possible is gathered from various sources. The next stage is information control and management (Balcar, 2014). Thus, through critical thinking, a distinction is made and specific information that is deemed valuable is chosen. The students then process the information in order to draw conclusions and gradually reveal possible solutions to the problem. The proposals - solutions that appear to satisfy the data and requirements of the problem until the students come up with specific solutions - are

presented next (Schulz, 2008). Throughout the process, the teacher supports and mentors the students, not providing the answer or solution, but providing the necessary impetus so that they continue until the end of the process. This guidance should take the form of "directed inquiry," in which the teacher provides the information the students will need, asks questions, and points so that the students can be led to verify or formulate conclusions.

Decision

Every day, all people are called upon to make decisions on various issues that concern them, ranging from very simple to complex and with significant implications. This skill does not work in isolation, but is linked to others such as critical thinking and problem-solving methods. Students use the decision-making process to look for possible or alternative solutions to a problem based on the criteria they initially set (Matsangouras, 2007). As they relate to logical, moral, and social criteria, these criteria may differ from person to person or from student to student. Students develop argumentation skills through the decision-making process. For every possible decision, consider the positives and negatives, the advantages and disadvantages in a variety of areas, and ultimately choose the most advantageous or efficient one. Through the arguments they will develop for each proposal, a reasoning will emerge that will guide their decision. Of course, they argue not only to themselves, but also to others when they work in a group setting and must persuade those around them of the correctness of their decisions (logical, moral, social, etc.). Arguing is an important part of the decision-making process. Argumentation, in the context of classroom dialogue, for Simon and Blume (1996) is developed on the taken-as-shared knowledge of the community, and is a prerequisite for establishing justification. According to the researchers, argumentation is a social process in which individuals try to regulate their intentions and interpretations through cooperation, verbally presenting a logical reasoning for their actions, and they are not only associated with a specific lesson but also with a specific situation or social circumstance (Patronis, Potari & Spiliotopoulou, 1999).

Teamwork

One of the most important skills for students to have, especially as they enter adulthood, is the ability to collaborate and work in a team setting. Of course, the school, with its traditional methods of education, and the educational system in general are still based on individual ability. Working in a team entails being able to function smoothly and effectively in collaboration with others, whether at school, socially, or professionally. Working in a team requires the ability to prioritize the interests of the group over the individual (Henderson-Hurley & Hurley, 2013). To be able to contribute his talents and abilities while assisting other members to give their all. This skill is related to social because it is necessary to maintain group balance. Also, his understanding and influence on issues requiring leadership (Robles, 2012).

Working in heterogeneous groups, in most cases, necessitates skills related to the individual's ability to collaborate as well as lead within the group. Also, the ability to form alliances with both general team members and specific individuals. It is also necessary to be able to listen to and respect the views and opinions of other members while also being able to redefine priorities and objectives as needed. Finally, it is critical to be able to resolve the inevitable conflicts that arise in a group as a whole (Shalini, 2013).

Metacognitive abilities

The term was coined by Stanford University psychologist John Flavell "Metacognition» in 1976 and linked it to the individual's capacity for self-knowledge and self-assessment. He also linked the term to strategies that a person can use to understand the world and evaluate his own knowledge, such as "the person may know that he is capable of adding and removing integers, but another person is better at solving original problems" (Cardelle-Elawar, 1995).

Metacognition is linked to problem solving and critical thinking abilities. These abilities are related to one another and belong to the individual's so-called higher abilities. Metacognitive skills are one of the most important goals in the field of education because they allow students to make effective use of their knowledge and gain insight into their potential. Furthermore, metacognitive skills assist an individual in controlling and evaluating their progress in a field. Furthermore,

metacognition is associated with the effort to improve the solutions proposed by the individual, leading him to self-improvement (Barkley, et al., 2014).

Capabilities for lifelong learning

The concept of lifelong learning is becoming more prevalent in educational research and texts. The days of a man acquiring specialization in a field and remaining in it for the rest of his life appear to be over. Thus, lifelong learning is one of the skills of the twenty-first century. People can learn new subjects and gain new knowledge through it, both in their field and in others. According to Demirel (2009), "lifelong learning" is a continuous process in which individuals develop their knowledge, skills, and seek opportunities for learning.

Individuals can broaden their knowledge and potential through both formal and non-formal education as part of lifelong learning. One of the skills related to it is digital literacy, which relates to their ability to keep up with current events. Through this skill, the individual gains the ability to innovate, which provides them with additional opportunities in a world that is constantly changing and diversifying (Taing et al., 2013).

This type of learning is concerned with individual and social development in all settings, including formal education (schools, vocational schools, higher education, and adult education institutions) and non-formal education (home, work, community). According to Bryce (2000), lifelong learning skills are important to cultivate in students as early as primary school because it is a focal point of change and evolution (Chamorro-Premuzic et al., 2010).

Soft skill development at school

As demonstrated in the preceding chapter, developing soft skills provides significant benefits and has a positive impact on many aspects of an individual's daily life. Soft skills can and should be developed through education in order to contribute to the complete development of each child's personality. There are numerous references to their development in the curricula, but there is no correlation with school textbooks and the philosophy on which they are based (OECD, 2018).

The traditional teaching method of acquiring knowledge and applying it through memorization is a significant impediment to the development of soft skills, as is the lack of teacher training on methods and techniques for their development. As a result, the problem focuses on these two critical factors: school textbooks and teachers' cognitive backgrounds. Concerning the first part of the problem, not only should textbooks be changed, but also the philosophy of learning practice (Shakirova, 2007). The implementation of modern teaching methods is critical to the development of soft skills at school. Soft skills can be developed using methods such as problem solving (Problem Solving Method), the project method (Project Learning Method), and STEM methodology. The role of the teacher is the second most important factor in the successful integration of soft skills into students' daily learning lives. The teacher does not operate in the traditional context, where he asks closed-ended questions and expects individual responses from each student. The students, not each one individually, play the central role in the new learning process. As a result, the center of gravity shifts away from the individual and toward the collective. This is a critical distinction that requires extra effort to put into practice. Students are given a project or a problem to solve in groups. They investigate the sources of the problem and its main characteristics, develop models of solutions, and arrive at some through discussion and argumentation. They then place them in the critical thinking of the other students and, if necessary, reconfigure their strategy by using different approaches (Laskey & Hetzel, 2010).

As the course provides these opportunities, the aforementioned process enables students to develop many soft skills in the same learning subject, both individually and collectively. Of course, for students who are used to the traditional teaching model, this new approach presents a challenge in which they must find new ways to follow. By taking on the central role of the lesson, students become more active participants and value aspects of their character on a daily basis. Furthermore, due to the differentiation of the educational method and the questions-problems assigned to them, students must adapt to the new way of teaching and the requirements it has. As a result, the teacher must anticipate and gradually involve them by organizing the lesson appropriately and providing the necessary assistance at all stages of the course.

Soft skills and the labor market

According to a 2020 report on soft skills, one of the main issues that appears to concern CEOs around the world is upskilling. The fourth industrial revolution introduced new business models and ways of working that necessitate critical new technical, digital, and soft skills. Working with these skills, even when properly developed, appears to be an exception and thus increasingly sought. People with soft skills can help businesses innovate. Thus, the solution to this modern problem appears to be a reconfiguration of the educational model to include the development of soft skills.

Business surveys conducted up to 2020 clearly show the direction in which companies are moving through their leaders. Specifically, some of the most important findings of PwC's "The following organizations have developed upskilling, according to the 23rd Annual Global CEO Survey»:

- 94% of leaders say they see higher innovation and accelerated digital transformation in their organization, and 93% say the skills gap and job-skills mismatch have narrowed, while employee productivity has increased.

- 95% of leaders report a stronger corporate culture and employee loyalty, and 93% report increased organizational growth.

According to the findings of the preceding study, the needs of businesses are shifting toward employees who have honed specific skills. The goal, however, is not for them to develop during people's adult lives, but for them to be gradually cultivated and made available to all students through the educational system. Thus, with concerted efforts, the educational model can be changed and reconfigured to ensure that people all over the world are productively engaged in meaningful work.

Soft Skills and Everyday Life

Soft skills and their role in the labor sector were discussed above, which is an important issue for young people. Soft skills and their role in people's daily lives will be discussed in this section. Through this lens, it will be seen that their development provides significant benefits to students who do not focus on a single area but compose a chapter for their entire life. "Soft skills" refer to abilities and behaviors related to how we interact with our fellow humans, friends, and acquaintances. Furthermore, soft skills are associated with issues such as communication, flexibility, innovation, passion, persuasiveness, extroversion, problem-solving, team spirit, time management, final result orientation, change management skills, and so on.

Communication Skills

Interpersonal and communication skills include the ability to hear and observe in order to truly understand. These are especially important in the classroom and, later, in our adult lives. Another aspect of communication skills is the ability to debate and effectively convey our thoughts and ideas orally or in writing. The way we externalize our thoughts and feelings is particularly important because it allows us to reveal our true selves. This ability is useful in everyday interactions because it allows us to persuade, influence, and encourage those around us.

Communication skills enable one to express oneself with correct and appropriate arguments and to motivate those around oneself in one's own unique way. These abilities are particularly beneficial to both modern teachers and students. Teachers can motivate students and assist them in adopting their teaching style. All members of a class can work in a team spirit, working together to achieve their goals, by creating a climate of communication.

Another benefit of communication skills is that they help not only to convey messages and communicate, but also to improve understanding, collaboration, and, as a result, to convey the right messages. As a result, every student should be motivated to develop these skills through the educational system.

Emotional Intelligence (EQ)

For many years, the weight of general intelligence as measured by IQ tests was placed at both the educational and work levels. However, they only reveal one aspect of a person's personality. Many researchers regard emotional intelligence as complementary, and its development and externalization can benefit anyone. Emotional intelligence determines how easily one can form relationships with others, put themselves in their shoes, and try to understand how they feel.

Using emotional intelligence, one can generate positive emotions and eventually gain the sympathy of others. Many students today struggle to highlight aspects of themselves, which is a problem that can be solved through the development and externalization of the emotional world. Emotional intelligence is important when working in groups because the different personalities of the students must find ways to communicate and work together toward a common goal. By putting themselves in the shoes of others, they can gain a better understanding of their way of thinking, the difficulties they face, and their overall perspective.

Teamwork abilities

During the learning process, students are frequently asked to work in groups on common projects or on activities that require them to collaborate with their classmates. Of course, cooperation is present in everyday life, both at home and in sports, activities, and so on. Teamwork abilities refer to a student's ability to work smoothly and effectively in collaboration with their classmates. He can help achieve the common goal by understanding his role and highlighting his potential. At the same time, each student must respect and assist his classmates while also encouraging them to highlight their interests and talents. As a result, students can encourage and inspire the other members of the group. Also, when someone is in a group situation, the feeling of understanding is especially important.

Flexibility/Adaptability

Because the environment around us is constantly changing, man must be able to adapt to the conditions that form around him. This skill becomes increasingly important as the individual's challenges increase. Because the situation is rapidly changing, it is necessary to be able to differentiate strategies and decision-making based on the circumstances. The way an individual evaluates and uses available information in order to reach conclusions and make sound decisions is critical in the new reality. As a result, it appears that this skill is related to other soft ones, such as critical thinking and problem solving.

Critical Pedagogy and Education

Critical Pedagogy, as a philosophy, is inherently anti-systemic effort and places the student at the center as a vehicle for changing the system. As a result, each student has the potential to effect significant change and differentiate the oppressive social model (Gounari & Grolios, 2010). Although the educational system mentioned above has a clear systemic orientation, the teacher has the freedom to choose the model of education and help students acquire a personal and free way of perceiving the social environment (Kantzara, 2010). Students can acquire and practice critical thinking skills through the learning process, which allows them to challenge dominant data. This is one of the first steps toward changing the social model and distinguishing it from the current one. This change will occur through action, not theory. She is the foundation of the entire structure, but it is her actions that will bring the old one down (Kalogiannakis, 2000).

Critical Pedagogy places a high value on students because they are the citizens of tomorrow, and their way of thinking will shape the future social system. As a result, every student matters, and the oppressed are the ones who are most in need of a way of thinking that will assist them in creating a vision for the society of tomorrow. They can recognize social issues at a young age because of education. problems and obstacles posed by the system and attempting to solve and reshape it. As a result, they will be able to become active citizens at a young age and recognize the critical importance of action in changing a social model (Giroux, 2010a).

Relationships between students and teachers in Critical Pedagogy

The student-teacher dipole is significant in the context of Critical Pedagogy because critical thinking can develop through the common path. It takes more than one to achieve it; a climate of trust must be created. Time also plays an important role, because developing critical thinking is not an easy and immediate result. On the contrary, it is possible for this different way of thinking to gradually mature through various activities and actions. Of course, the teacher must direct the action toward specific areas, and it is up to the students to solve or improve specific issues. As many problems have already been identified, they can gradually change and shape the context in which they live. Reforming the framework is critical because it is what will allow people to shape the society they

want rather than the one that has already been built for them (Freeman, 1992). The development of a different way of thinking can assist students in breaking free from the framework that has been structured by the system and imposes on them a specific type of knowledge and skills that are exclusively related to the labor market and immerse them in a social context. They have the opportunity to develop their personality in a different way and structure a personal way of thinking through Critical Pedagogy. Critical theory's philosophy does not seek a specific way of thinking, but rather the liberation of the individual through his personal experience. In this manner, they will be able to effect the necessary changes (Alexiou, 2009).

With important theorists Aronowitz, Giroux, and McLaren, as well as Freire, a new direction is given to critical theory as it differentiates and focuses more on the problems and requirements of modern times. The emergence of socioeconomic problems necessitates the involvement of a school (Aronowitz, 2010). The school now has a new role that goes far beyond providing sterile knowledge to traditional educational standards. According to Giroux and McLaren, the school was used to serve the claims for decades. In fact, the education system is linked to the socioeconomic establishment, so that it serves the above interests and, in the end, students accept the situation they encounter, lacking the mood and skills to pursue change. In this way, they are prepared to convert to the next workers and even fully accept the social model that has been established (McLaren, 2000).

Critical pedagogy and the development of soft skills

Critical Pedagogy is associated with the development of soft skills because the goal is no longer the acquisition of knowledge but the complete formation of students' character and way of thinking, away from social stereotypes. Students can form a critical way of thinking and approach problems in their daily lives by using this new approach to the lesson, which they could not do with traditional education. Students have the freedom to approach the requested issues from their own point of view and seek solutions based on their own way of thinking because the teacher creates the appropriate conditions. Gradually, as they gain more experience and develop their skills, they will be able to think critically about the everyday problems they are confronted with, as well as the social environment that has formed around them. Thus, the problem-solving method and the soft skills associated with and developed through this approach are extremely important for the child's way of thinking. This approach pits the student against the problem, rather than the group against a demand that must be reconfigured and resolved through group thought and action. Thus, the student operates in a group and collaborative context while learning how to deal with difficulties and major problems. Individuals are not a solution; only through a coordinated group effort can the necessary changes be brought about. Learning and knowledge are not handed down by the teacher as omniscient, but are discovered by the students through a critical process. Each of the soft skills mentioned in the first chapter has a place in the learning process that is organized around the principles of Critical Pedagogy.

Conclusions

Soft skills are an important chapter in the general skills of modern man, both in his social and work environments. However, the traditional way of perceiving knowledge in the education system emphasizes the development of "hard" skills rather than soft ones. Of course, in a constantly changing environment, it appears that developing soft skills is the answer to new challenges. Citizens can keep up with societal and economic demands through them. Their integration into educational reality is slow. Of course, the context in which they are placed is important. Critical pedagogy is a pedagogical theory that can be used to help students understand the world around them and acquire the necessary intellectual skills to change it. The development of critical thinking is not only one of the soft skills, but it also plays an important role in how the child perceives the world and his surroundings. As a result, a system designed to trample it underfoot must be changed. However, this shift must result from a shift in perception as well as action. Other soft skills development is essential in this context.

The development of soft skills has entered many education systems around the world, as their importance in many aspects of people's lives is internationally and scientifically recognized. People can cope with demands and improve their lives and daily lives by growing. Teacher-centered teaching models cannot be developed in Greece's traditional and centralized educational system, and students

fall short of important skills. The development of new innovative learning programs can help in this regard. At the same time, the incorporation of new technologies provides additional learning incentives and promotes active participation by all students. As a result, new technologies become a part of everyday learning reality as a tool in the hands of the teacher. The context in which the above is included, the development of soft skills through the use of new technologies, can be done within the context of critical pedagogy. As a result, students have the opportunity to develop a new transformative way of thinking away from the data of the socioeconomic system and redefine their place in it. Developing their critical thinking will assist them in democratizing the school with the ultimate goal and goal of democratizing the society they will be called upon to live in, thus achieving action as a tool for reshaping the system.

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ТОМ 1, НОМЕР 1

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VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1